

Command-Button Hard-Stops in Automotive Environment

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Abstract. Rotary knobs are used as a common human-machine interface (HMI). Recently an innovative solution has been developed to produce variable detents with minimal power consumption and no moving parts. This solution ensures silent and wear-resistant operation based on the use of an electro-permanent magnet (EPM). This paper introduces three additional solutions to simulate a hard-stop (HS) sensation during knob rotation, preventing unintended activations or to signal that a limit has been reached.

Keywords: automotive, haptic, hard stop, HMI, knob

1 Context

In modern vehicles, where physical interfaces are fewer, the demand for HMI feedback has grown for safety and operational purposes. For example, knob-type gear shifters require HS for safety but often rely on bulky and noisy motorized locks [1]-[3]. Built on the EPM knob concept described in details in [4], [5], three new electromagnetic solutions for achieving HS functionality are proposed.

The primary aim of this article is to investigate how various electromagnetic HS modules, using different physical phenomena, influence the haptic perception of button behaviour. To achieve this objective, three buttons have been developed, prototyped, and tested.

A user study was conducted to compare these three buttons and identify the one that provides the most pleasant haptic feedback and suited for automotive environments.

2 Proposed Hard-Stop Knobs

To provide the detents, almost the same EPM knob concept was used for all the three knobs, while the HS feature was insured using three different physical phenomena.

The first rotary knob is entirely based on the initial EPM-based solution, without moving parts. Depending on the intensity of the current pulse, the residual magnetization of the low coercivity (H_c) magnet can be controlled. This allows the ratchet mode to be activated with a low current pulse and the HS mode to be obtained with a higher current level. Simply the torque amplitude difference provides a feeling of HS.

The second knob solution adds two small movable magnetic rollers that go into contact with the knob. The proper angle of contact establishes a self-locking clutch within the system which locks alternatively the displacement only in one way depending on the magnetization direction and amplitude of a second low Hc magnet.

Finally, the third knob proposal has a different EPM design with 2 phases and a locking pin. The stator has one magnet with high Hc and two coils wound around low Hc magnets. When the magnets are oriented in such a way that the magnetic field passes through the locking pin, it generates a force that moves the pin to interfere with the rotor teeth.

In all the proposed solutions, to switch from one mode to the other, the coils are briefly energized (magnetization in few μs) which makes the system very efficient.

Table 1. Proposed HS mechanisms working principle and characteristics.

	Fully magnetic locking	Bi-directional control-lable clutch	Mechanical lock with control capability
Later called	#1	#2	#3
Functioning principle			
Dimensions		Ø60mm x H30mm	
Type of lock	Magnetic		Mechanical
HS torque	1.75 Nm	> 0.8 Nm	> 8 Nm
Contact stiff.	$\approx 0.35 \text{ Nm/}^\circ$	$\approx 0.16 \text{ Nm/}^\circ$	> 1.2 Nm/°
Lock. time	< 6 ms	< 2.5 ms	< 10 ms
Mass (total)	550 g	210g	180g
Mass (PM)	75 g	20g	20 g
Prototypes			

3 User study

In the user study, 18 people have evaluated the haptic perception of three prototypes. Participants provide their evaluations using a survey consisting of seven questions aiming to rank the buttons on their hard-stop feeling, based on criteria as the noise or the stiffness of the contact as well has their perceived quality. The responses to the survey are summarized in the table below, presenting the obtained tendencies in percentage.

Table 2. Summary of the user study results.

Quality of the HS feeling			Definitiveness (haptic wall stiffness)			Noise		
#1	#2	#3	#1	#2	#3	#1	#2	#3
100% Double click at the HS position								
Classification			Definition of pleasant for the majority					
Worst Best			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The distinct sensation of switching from rotation mode to HS mode; - Acoustic discretion; - Haptic detection of the stop position with no risk of accidental overshoot and damage. 					

4 Conclusion

The results of this study highlight the diversity of participant preferences with regard to the haptic sensation of HS produced by the knob when they come to a stop. While some participants prefer a definitive and unambiguous stop, others appreciate the ability to make slight additional motion. In addition, some participants prefer completely silent action, while others prefer a subtle mechanical sound.

The knob with bi-directional controllable clutch proved to be the preferred solution for the majority of the testers because it provides a clear and distinct HS feeling.

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